

Conductive Plastics Mixed with Metal Fiber

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ABSTRACT

This paper relates the electrical and thermal properties of the conductive plastics mixed with the metal fibers, which were manufactured by "Chatter Machining" newly developed by the authors. The electrical conductivity and the electro-magnetic interference(EMI) shielding properties of the composites made by the injection molding or the compression molding were mainly investigated in this experiments, and the measurement system of the EMI shielding effectiveness was also discussed. It was experimentally confirmed that the specific resistance of this composite remarkably decreased with the increase of content and aspect ratio of fibers. Under 0.07 ohm-cm was achieved when 15% volume of brass and copper fibers with the suitable size were mixed and these conductive composites showed the sufficient EMI shielding effectiveness. In regard to the thermal properties, the composite containing 15 volume % Al alloy fiber with the aspect ratio of 40 has 30 times conductivity in comparison with that of matrix polymer itself. Hence the conductive composites seem to be applicable for the materials of housings of electric and electronic devices.

1. INTRODUCTION

Most of housings for electric and electronic devices are made of plastic polymer, because they have sufficient flexibility in designing their shapes and can accomplish the lightening of the devices. As the plastic polymer has no electric conductivity, the housing made of plastics has no ability to prevent the static charge and the electro-magnetic interference(EMI), the heat generated in the device does not rapidly dissipate from the housing due to the poor thermal conductivity of plastics. In order to provide plastic parts with the electric and thermal conductivity, there are techniques such as coating, metallizing and compounding of conductive fillers. It may be advantageous to use the composites including conductive fillers, when the shielding effectiveness(SE), the long term reliability and the processing cost are taken into consideration. Though the fibrous fillers are considered to be superior to other conductive fillers like as powder particles or flakes, no fibrous filler which can satisfy the requirement of the economical feasibility had not been found. Because the existing fibrous fillers such as chopped stainless steel, carbon fiber and metal coated glass fiber are manufactured through costly processes. On the other hand, the new manufacturing process of short length metal fiber has been developed recently by the authors at Inst. of Ind. Sci., Univ. of

Tokyo. By this process the short length metal fiber with suitable dimensions for the filler of the plastic composites can be produced efficiently, and then this fiber is said to be supplied with fairly low price.

This paper mainly describes the experimental results in the electrical conductivity and the EMI shielding property of plastic composites using this metal fiber and the thermal and mechanical properties of this composites are also related.

2. MANUFACTURING PROCESS OF METAL FIBER BY CHATTER MACHINING

The short metal fiber is directly produced from metal rod by a lathe-turning operation as illustrated schematically in Fig.1. The self-excited vibration, which is generally called as chattering is utilized positively to separate the machined chip into the fiber. The specially designed elastic cutting tool is used to obtain the large and stable vibration. The diameter of fiber can be easily controlled by changing the cutting conditions such as the cutting speed and the feed rate, and the length of fiber corresponds to the depth or width of cut. The dimensional range of fiber which can be produced in the chatter machining is varied from 10 - 500 μm in diameter and 0.5-250 mm in length.

Any kinds of metal fibers considered to be suitable for the conductive filler such as steel, aluminium and its alloys, copper and its alloys as bronze and brass can be produced. As is clear from the cross sectional geometry and the appearance of chatter machined fiber as shown in Fig. 2, the fiber has triangular-section and has rough rugged surfaces and a smooth surface. From these fiber configurations, it is supposed to give the adequate bonding strength between the fiber and the plastic polymer. This fiber has larger surface area than a fiber with round cross section.

Fig.1 Schematic manufacturing process of fine short length metal fibers by Chatter Machining

Fig.2 Appearances and cross section of short length metal fiber used in the experiment

3. FABRICATION OF THE FIBROUS COMPOSITES

Three typical molding processes, the injection molding, the compression molding and the casting molding were chosen to make test pieces of the conductive composites. Aluminium alloy, copper and brass fibers were prepared for the conductive fillers with the consideration of their anti-corrosion properties. Aluminium alloy fiber, which has 50 μm in diameter and 1 - 3 mm in length, brass fiber having a length of 3mm and a diameter of 50 μm and copper fibers having a length of 2.5mm and a diameter of 40 μm were used after considering their mixing ability into matrix which is very much affected by the aspect ratio of the fiber. Any surface treatment to improve the electrical conductivity was not provided to the fiber. Matrix polymers of the conductive composites used here were Nylon-6, Polyethylen, AS and ABS as resins for thermoplastic materials and Epoxy resin as thermoset material. Fibers and thermoplastic resins were compounded with the screw type extruder and then the extruded composite strings were chopped with the pelletizer to make polymer pellets including metal fibers. Thermoplastic pellets premixed with the metal fiber can be utilized in

the two kinds of molding methods, the injection molding and the compression molding. A tensile test specimen and a plaque with 3mm thick used for EMI shielding test were prepared by the conventional injection molding machine. In the injection molding, in general, fibers were well dispersed and were not so much orientated as shown in Fig.3. However, some of fibers were recognized to be bend or parted off when the aspect ratio and the content of the fiber were large Fig.4, which make the electric conductivity poor. Such problem could be avoided by selection suitable molding conditions such as temperature, pressure and nozzle diameter. On the other hand, the liquid thermoset epoxy resin was mixed with the fiber and then the compound was poured into the plaque mold made of brass. Dimensional accuracy of the molded parts is not treated here, but it is already confirmed that the shrinkage of composites was reduced very much as compared with the matrix polymer itself.

Fig.3 Photograph showing fiber dispersion observed by soft X-ray (injection molded plaque, $V_f=15\%$)

Fig.4 Appearances of metal fibers in the injection molded composite (Nylon 6 + 15 vol % Al alloy fiber)

4. ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF COMPOSITES

4.1 Measuring of electrical conductivity

In order to give such electric properties to these composites as the prevention of static charge, heating by an electric current and EMI shielding, the composites must have an adequate electrical conductivity which is generally expressed by the specific resistance.

The electrical resistances between both ends and surfaces of the plaque were measured by using a digital multimeter. Measuring methods were illustrated in Fig. 5. In the measurement of the resistance between both ends, the ends of the molded plaque were ground to remove the thin surface resin-rich layer and they were coated with the conductive silver paint. On the other hand, the conductivity between both surfaces were measured as molded without giving any surface treatment and in the state of compression with the brass conductive rings to ensure good electrical contact.

Fig.5 Two measuring methods for electrical conductivity of composite

4.2 Electrical conductivity

The specific resistance of the injection molded specimen decreases with the increase of fiber content and the increase of aspect ratio (l/d) of the fiber as shown in Fig. 6. The electrical conductivity less than 10^{-1} ohm-cm could be obtained when the 15 vol % fiber having aspect ratio of 40 ($l=2\text{mm}$, $d=50\mu\text{m}$) was mixed into matrix resin. On the other hand, the surface resistance is higher than that of former by as much as several hundred times as shown in Fig.7. This is due to the resin rich layer around the surfaces which was not removed in this measurement. The influence of fiber material on the specific resistance of the composites was measured using compression molded plaques with different fibers of aluminium alloy, brass and copper. As is given in Table 1, the composite including copper fiber shows the highest conductivity among them, and the

composite with aluminium alloy fiber shows the lowest conductivity. This may come from the difference in the surface resistance of fiber itself due to the surface oxidation. The reason for the difference in the electrical conductivity between both specimens prepared by the injection molding and by the compression molding, is considered that the extent of fiber breakage is lower in the compression molding specimen.

Fig.6 Effect of fiber content to specific resistance between opposing ends Fig. 7 Effect of fiber content to specific resistance between opposing surfaces

Plastic composites	Specific resistance between opposing ends ρ_B (ohm-cm)
ABS + Copper fiber(10 vol.%)	0.067
ABS + Brass fiber (10 vol.%)	0.075
ABS + Al alloy fiber(10 vol.%)	0.100

Table 1 Specific resistance between opposing ends(compression molding)

5. EMI SHIELDING OF METAL FIBER MIXED PLASTICS

5.1 Measuring of EMI shielding

Shielding properties for EMI are said to be the most important feature required for conductive plastics. The shielding effectiveness (SE) for EMI is roughly estimated from the specific resistance of the composites. However, the real value of SE has to be expressed by the ratio of the amount of energy that would pass through the material to the incident energy using a large conductive panel in the free space. Since the very costly and huge shielded room should be used for the measurement of shielding effectiveness, simplified methods using a small shielded box installing a pair of antennas have been developed for the sake of experimental measurement. In the experiment of SE measurement three types of small boxes were manufactured and their properties were investigated using a spectrum analyzer before the SE test.

To know the SE of composites thoroughly, three types of shielding effectiveness in the magnetic field mode, electric field mode and plane wave mode have to be measured. Accordingly, the shield box and the antennas by which the shielding effectiveness in three modes can be measured in the wide range of the frequencies, have to be prepared. Four antenna types and three types of small shielding box were manufactured for the experimental measurement as given in Fig. 8. One is a plate antenna used for the small box type A which is proposed by Rockwell International corporation. The second and the third are a small loop antenna operated in the magnetic field mode and a small rod antenna operated in the electric field mode. Both of above two antennas were

used for the small box type B and their shapes and sizes were carefully determined by considering MILL standard to cover the wide range of frequencies from 1 MHz to 1000 MHz. The fourth is a 18 cm long conical rod antenna that is operated in the approximate plane wave mode and used for small box type C, which was designed by Dr.Hasebe (Nippon Univ).

As shown in Fig. 10(a), it was recognized that the combination of type A box and a plate antenna showed a somewhat curious curve which may be affected by resonance observed at frequencies around 500 and 600 MHz. Judging from the shape of antenna, it is not clear in which mode the measurement is carried out by this device(Type A).

Fig.8 Three types of shielding boxes

Fig.9 Characteristic curves of small shielding box

In contrast with the above shielding box A, newly designed type B box showed stable characteristics in the electric field mode and the magnetic field mode. It is rather hard to measure the shielding effectiveness in the plane wave mode using such a small shielding box because the distance between each antennas has to be set far longer than the wave length. However, as the result of investigations on the shape and the size of the shield box and antennas, the SE of the plane wave mode could be measured stably by the box C as shown in Fig. 9(c).

5.2 Shielding effectiveness

The plaque with 200 x 200 x 3mmt in the size, which was manufactured by the compression molding using premixed ABS pellets with the metal fiber($V_f=10\%$) was confirmed to have the shielding properties as shown in Fig. 10, where the SE in the electric field mode, the magnetic field mode and the plane wave mode, was measured using the type B and C boxes for the composites including different metal fibers of copper, brass and aluminium alloy respectively. The composites including copper and brass fibers showed excellent shielding effectiveness of more than 30 dB in the wide range of frequencies, whereas the composites including aluminium alloy fiber showed a less shielding effectiveness. Though the SE in the magnetic field mode is less than that in the electric field mode, the composites with brass or copper fiber is considered to have sufficient shielding effectiveness even in the former mode. Since the difference in the SE by the difference of fiber materials previously shown in Fig. 10 was considered to be due to the conductivity of the composites, the relations between the specific resistance and the shielding effectiveness at the frequency of 800 MHz was investigated using various composites manufactured by different methods such as the injection molding, the compression molding and the casting molding. From the result shown in Fig. 11, it can be said that the SE increases with the decrease of the specific resistance in the region of 0.07 - 0.11 ohm-cm and the SE keeps almost constant under 0.07 ohm-cm. The SE and the electrical conductivity of the composites produced by the injection molding are rather inferior to those of the compression molded and the casting molded composites.

Fig. 10 SE in three modes measured using type B and C boxes

Fig. 11 Relation between SE in three modes and specific resistances (opposing ends)

This is mainly due to the fiber breakage occurred at pelletizing and injection molding when the improper processing conditions were used. To avoid such a problem and to get better shielding properties, the kinds of material and the size of fiber mixed in and the molding conditions have to be carefully selected.

6. THERMAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

6.1 Thermal conductivity

The improvement in the thermal conductivity is also expected when the metal fibers are mixed into the plastic material. This is desirable to the housings of the electric and electronic devices as the heat generated in the housings can be easily dissipated. As given in Fig. 12 showing the relation between the thermal conductivity of the composites and the fiber content, the thermal conductivity was increased and became 30 times of plastic polymer itself when 15 vol % aluminium alloy fibers with 2 mm in length were mixed into it.

Fig. 12 Improvement in thermal conductivity

(K_c : Thermal conductivity of composite)
(K_p : Thermal conductivity of plastics)

6.2 Heating properties

The composites including metal fiber can be heated by the microwave. As the matrix polymer surrounding metal fiber is heated via metal fiber in this case, the time required for heating decreases with the increase of fiber content as shown in Fig. 13. This makes the heating time of conductive composites shorter when the subsequent hot processing is required in the stamp forming of fibrous composites. It may be possible to apply this conductive composites to the plate heater. Fig. 14 shows the change of the surface temperature of composites heated by flowing an electric current in the plate of composites. The temperature reaches a constant value. This is because of the increased electric resistance accompanying with the temperature rise shown in Fig. 15, which comes from the release of fiber contact due to the difference of thermal expansion between matrix polymer and metal fiber.

Fig. 13 Heating of composite with metal fiber by the irradiation of micro wave

Fig. 14 Heating property by flowing an electric current

Fig. 15 Change of resistance with temperature

6.3 Mechanical properties

The results of the tensile test are shown in Fig. 16. Elastic Young's Modulus increases remarkably with the increase of fiber content and reaches up to 200 kg/mm² at 20 vol % fiber content, while the tensile strength does not change. Though the tensile elongation of the composites decreases with the increase of fiber content, it is confirmed from the impact strength test that the fracture toughness value of fibrous composites is far higher than those of the composites with conductive powder particles or flakes.

Fig. 16 Mechanical properties of plastic composites with metal fiber [Steel fiber(1=1mm,d=35μm)+HDPE]

7. CONCLUSIONS

New type of short metal fiber produced by chatter machining was mixed into plastics to make conductive composites, and various properties of the composites such as electrical conductivity, EMI shielding effectiveness and thermal and mechanical properties were investigated. The main results obtained are as follows;

1. The composites including the chatter machined metal fiber can be formed successfully not only by the casting molding and the compression molding but also by the injection molding.
2. Electrical conductivity of the composites was improved with the increase of the aspect ratio and the content of the fiber, and the specific resistance of the composites was reduced to 0.1 ohm-cm in the injection molded specimen and 0.07 ohm-cm in the compression molded one.
3. Shielding effectivenesses in the electric field mode, the magnetic field mode and the plane wave mode were measured using the improved small shielding boxes. Shielding effectiveness in the electric field mode reached 40 dB, whereas in the magnetic field mode it reached 30 dB when the composites include 15 vol % fibers. And it was confirmed that the fibrous composites have sufficient ability in EMI shielding.
4. Fibrous conductive composites have the improved thermal conductivity. The composite with the appropriate electric resistance can be used for plate heater.
5. Though the elastic modulus of the fibrous composite increases in proportion to the fiber content, the elongation is reduced as the content increases.

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